

THE IMPACT OF MACROECONOMIC FACTORS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESSES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This study empirically analyzes the impact of macroeconomic factors on the growth of gross value created by small businesses based on panel data from 14 regions of Uzbekistan for the period 2010-2024. In addition, the calculation method includes the level of economic activity, debt obligations of small businesses, employment share, and foreign investment indicators as explanatory factors. The results of the fixed effect model used in the study indicate the importance of the impact of the macroeconomic factors selected in the study on the development of small businesses in the country

Keywords: small business, macroeconomic indicators, Uzbekistan

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda O‘zbekistonning 2010-2024 yillar oralig‘idagi 14 ta hududning panel ma’lumotlari asosida, kichik tadbirkorlik subyektlari tomonidan yaratiladigan yalpi qiymatning o‘shishiga makroiqtisodiy omillarning ta’siri empirik tahlil qilingan holda o‘rganiladi. Undan tashqari hisoblash usuliga tushuntiruvchi omillar sifatida iqtisodiy faollik darajasi, kichik biznes subyektlarining qarz majburiyatlari, bandlik ulushi hamda xorijiy investitsiyalar ko‘rsatkichlari ham kiritiladi. Tadqiqotda qo‘llanilgan fixed effect modelining natijalari mamlakatdagi kichik tadbirkorlik subyektlarining rivojlanishiga tadqiqotda tanlab olingan makroiqtisodiy omillarning ta’sir doirasi muhimligini ko‘rsatadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: kichik biznes, makroiqtisodiy ko‘rsatkichlar, O‘zbekiston

Аннотация. В данном исследовании эмпирически анализируется влияние макроэкономических факторов на рост валовой стоимости, создаваемой малым бизнесом, на основе панельных данных по 14 регионам Узбекистана за период 2010-2024 годов. Кроме того, в метод расчета включены такие объясняющие факторы, как уровень экономической активности, задолженность малых предприятий, доля занятости и показатели иностранных инвестиций. Результаты модели с фиксированными эффектами, использованной в исследовании, указывают на значимость влияния выбранных в исследовании макроэкономических факторов на развитие малого бизнеса в стране

Ключевые слова: малый бизнес, макроэкономические показатели, Узбекистан

Introduction

In recent years, small businesses in Uzbekistan have emerged as a sector of great importance for sustainable economic growth. In particular, they are gaining importance in increasing employment, diversifying incomes, and supporting regional development. The reason is that the huge opportunities in recent years, namely the availability of financial resources and investment flows, have a direct impact on the expansion of the activities of small businesses. However, despite the increasing activity of small businesses, research on the macroeconomic factors affecting their development, specifically on the example of territorial segments, is relatively limited. Therefore, the assessment of factors that are important for small business activities and affect the development of the sector through empirical analysis is also an urgent issue from the point of view of economic policy.

The study conducts econometric analysis using the fixed effects approach. Based on the results obtained, it can be seen that the activities of small business entities are directly related to changes in the macroeconomic environment of the country. In particular, it confirms that financial resources and employment factors play an important role in its development. The results of the study can serve as a scientific basis for improving mechanisms for supporting small business entities in optimizing policy on the issue of regional economy in Uzbekistan.

Literature review

In scientific works that study the factors affecting small business entities, it is common in many literatures to distinguish between internal and external factors affecting them. This is because many studies determine the influence of internal resources on small businesses, but also indirectly related to the macroeconomic environment. Because it has been found that factors such as GDP growth, exchange rate, and trade openness significantly affect such business entities, even though they are small [1]. Of course, there are also sources that point to other scientific findings that the impact of macroeconomic indicators is certainly present for small businesses, for example, economic growth, government policy, access to capital, and human capital as key determinants of small and medium-sized business performance [2]. They also emphasized the crucial role of external environmental factors in the development of small businesses and firms [3].

In the case of Uzbekistan, some sources have indeed emphasized that the growth rate of the country's GDP is very important for the development of small businesses [4]. Because most of the studies conducted at the national level have confirmed through empirical analysis that the development of small business activities is the main driver of the national economy and that the share of small businesses and the volume of investments are related to the dynamics of GDP [5].

At the same time, some international scientific studies show that small business activity is sensitive to infrastructure, financial resources and market conditions. At the same time, they emphasize that the macroeconomic environment, which is considered an external environmental factor, also plays an important role in their growth [6]. All of the above literature suggests that there are empirical links between small business entities and macroeconomic factors, but there is a relative scarcity of research on this topic using regional panel data, specifically in Uzbekistan. Therefore, the results of this study are intended to partially fill the existing scientific gap.

Research methodology

In the Research Work, the assessment was carried out based on the following regression equation:

$$\ln \text{small_busi_sumit} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 \ln \text{GDPit} + \beta_2 \ln \text{DEPTit} + \beta_3 \text{small_bus_shareit} + \beta_4 \ln \text{FDIit} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Description of variables:

- $\log(\text{small_business_sum})$: Dependent variable – logarithmic value of the volume of gross product created by small businesses.
- $\log(\text{gdp})$: Logarithm of GDP in the territorial section.
- $\log(\text{debt})$: Total credit debt of small businesses is logarithmized.
- $\text{small_business_share}$: The share of the employed population that is engaged in small business (in percent).
- $\log(\text{fdi})$: Foreign direct investment attracted to the region.
- α_i – fixed effects specific to the region,
- ε_{it} – random error term.

The study used Stata software to evaluate the model, and the reliability of the results was checked through standard errors.

Results

Table 1. Impact of macroeconomic factors to small businesses (fixed effects)

	(1)	(2)
	logsmall_business_sum	logsmall_business_sum
log_gdp	0.936*** (0.025)	
log_debt	0.045*** (0.015)	0.065*** (0.018)
log_fdi	0.010 (0.007)	0.016* (0.008)
small_business_share	0.041*** (0.003)	0.036*** (0.004)
L1_GDP		0.878*** (0.029)
_const	21.183*** (0.371)	21.683*** (0.454)
Observations	195	195

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Source: Author’s calculation

If we turn to the results obtained using the fixed effects model in Table 1 of the study, we can see that small business activity is significantly dependent on macroeconomic factors. The volume of gross regional value has a positive coefficient in both models and is statistically significant. This means that an increase in overall economic activity also increases the volume of gross value created by the small business sector. In addition, it can be seen that the volume of credit attracted by small business enterprises and firms also has a statistically significant and positive coefficient on the growth of economic value created by them. This indicates that the expansion of access to financial resources is associated with an increase in the volume of activity. As a result, an increase in the share of the population employed in small businesses also leads to an increase in the gross value created by them, and according to the analysis, it has a statistically scientific basis, like the above variables.

The effect of foreign investment in the model did not produce relatively stable results. Only the second estimation method is statistically significant at 10%, which can be noted as a positive effect on the increase in the value created by small businesses. The lagged gross

regional value indicator in the dynamic specification also has a strong positive effect, indicating the presence of inertia and continuity in time in the development of small businesses.

In general, it can be confirmed that the growth of small business activity is highly dependent on the share of the population employed in it, the value of loans that can be provided to them, and, of course, the level of economic activity in the country.

Conclusion and recommendations

The study conducted an econometric analysis of the impact of macroeconomic factors on small business activity using panel data from 14 regions of Uzbekistan. The results of the analysis using the fixed effects estimation method showed that the level of economic activity of the country's regions, access to financial resources, and the share of employment significantly affect the volume of gross regional value created by small business entities. Although it was found that the inflow of foreign direct investment has a volatile effect on small businesses, it was found that it is closely related to economic activity, employment, and access to credit resources.

Based on the results obtained, the following recommendations can be put forward:

First, it is more appropriate to optimize credit interest rates for them and expand access to financial resources, while applying policies aimed at supporting small business activities. On the other hand, it may also be important to increase the number of programs that are considered important in increasing the share of the population employed in small businesses. Finally, it is also important to pay attention to indirect factors supporting small business entities in the regions and stimulate their economic activity.

In conclusion, this small study has shown that macroeconomic activity and the environment are very important in the development of small business activities. If further research is carried out on the basis of a wider set of variables or other econometric approaches, such scientific research can shed more light on this issue and offer more complete solutions.

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